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AMIR TUMUR AND HIS MANAGEMENT PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract: *Great strategist, skillful politician, strict reformer of outdated social relations, patron of trade, handicrafts and culture, Amir Temur established a state based on laws and traditions, invented specific features of the country's management, which ensured the greatness of his state.*

Key words: *Timurid statehood, Timurid era, Timurid kingdom, Timurid dynasty, Tzuklar.*

Amir Temur founded a large centralized state, different in terms of content. With this, he ensured the greatness of his people. Later, the statehood founded by Amir Temur took a place in the history page with names such as "The Timurid statehood", "The Timurid era", "The Timurid kingdom", "The Timurid dynasty". Great strategist, skillful politician, strict reformer of outdated social relations, patron of trade, crafts and culture, Amir Temur established a state based on laws and traditions.

Taking into account the specific features of our statehood, the service of Amir Temur, who was able to free himself from the Mongol invaders who tried to establish a statehood based on oppression and hard work, is particularly incomparable in history. Opposing the Mongols and expelling them from the country was not easy. If we draw attention to the opinions of the Arab historian Ibn al-Asir (1260-1233), who was a witness of the events of that time, about the Mongols, we will confirm the above opinion. "Day and night there was an unprecedented disaster that covered everything, especially the wealth created by Muslims. If someone said that the world has not seen anything like this since Allah Almighty created man, he would be telling the truth. Indeed, in the annals there was no similar or equal to such a great disaster. Among the events described in them, Nebuchadnezzar's act of beating the Israelites and destroying Jerusalem is the most terrible. But what happened to Jerusalem in front of the countries destroyed by these cursed people (Mongols)? Every city in these countries doubles up to Jerusalem. What happened to the Israelites compared to the people who were wiped out by the Mongols? After all, in one city, the Mongols beat more people than all the Israelites. They didn't spare anyone: they brutally beat women, men, and babies, ripped open pregnant women's bellies, and killed children."

Even at that time, our grandfather Amir Temur was responsible for resisting and throwing away the Mongol invaders, who were called "more than sand" and "man-

eaters released from chains". Entrepreneur Amir Temur appeared as a great politician and a skilled statesman.

Many generals and statesmen have passed the stage of history. Amir Temur, unlike them, came up with the specific features of managing the state, the country, which ensured the greatness of his state. Like other rulers, he did not rely on one or two classes, but on many classes of the people. These classes are:

1) sayyids (descendants of the prophet), scholars, mashoyikhs, virtuous people, i.e. intellectuals; 2) wise people who know the truth of the matter; 3) pious, dervish, Qalandars; 4) noyons (khanzodas, district, i.e. commanders of 10,000-strong army); 5) sipoh and raiyat, i.e. soldiers and common people; 6) special, i.e. trusted persons; 7) ministers and secretaries; 8) governors, doctors, astrologers and engineers; 9) tafsir and hadith scholars; 10) industrial people (artisans, artisans); 11) Sufis; 12) merchant (trader) and tourists.

"I compiled the rules and regulations of my kingdom into twelve categories. I considered these twelve categories to be the twelve constellations of my kingdom and the twelve months of the enterprise of my state," says Amir Temur.

During the time of Amir Temur, there were many processes, such as personal life and society, war and peace in society, harmony and conflict between citizens, a unique lifestyle, which required great strength, knowledge, wisdom, and skill to manage these processes. . It was difficult to build a great state without a deep understanding of the mutual relations inherent in these processes. Therefore, Amir Temur's views on statehood are based on modern philosophical teachings. After all, His Highness was well aware of the experience of the rulers and generals, prophets, caliphs, scholars, scientists and sages who passed before him, as well as the achievements of religious teachings, science and culture. Analyzing the twelve principles mentioned by Amir Temur, we believe that Amir is a great strategist, politician and philosopher. The principles of Timurid are important directions in state management, and they are a unique expression of the philosophy of statehood. Therefore, it can be concluded that A. Temur's philosophy focuses on connections and relationships. All links and connections in "Tuzuklar" have the following character:

- causal connections and relationships in events;
- important and non-important connections and relationships;
- mediated and unmediated connections and relationships;
- necessary and accidental connections and relationships.

If we analyze these connections and relationships separately, they, in their turn, cause further connections and relationships through interaction. For example, public administration is connected with many factors, at its core there is a complex philosophy and countless processes. When you understand one of them, a second truth emerges from it. Therefore, it is necessary to know the nature of events, to examine all

relevant aspects and tools as a whole. Only then will the development of events be ensured without mistakes. At the same time, different methods are used to determine them.

It should be noted that because our grandfather Amir Temur had an excellent philosophical way of thinking, he completed everything he started and achieved success. After all, connection and connection itself have philosophical deterministic (connection, communication, interaction) features. Amir Temur used principles in his work. If we analyze the first of the principles from the point of view of causal connections, that is, the main reason for strictly following the religion of God and the Sharia of the Prophet Muhammad, first of all, the socio-political environment of that time was taken into account. During the time when Amir Temur lived, Islam was recognized as a real force in the mind and thinking of the people in the land of Turan. This perfect divine teaching was absorbed into the hearts of the people. Naturally, His Highness Amir Temur strictly adhered to the tenets of the Islamic religion and adopted Islamic ideals as the main motto of his rule in the country. He built madrasas and mosques. He respected the religious leaders. As a result, the king always won. As a result of the promotion of Islam, the supporters of Sahibkiran increased, and the power of the state increased. In the management of a powerful state, it is clearly visible that the dependence of the second principle is subordinate to the first principle, that is, the reliance on people of different classes and categories in politics was born out of necessity. In connection with people, more precisely, with castes and categories (the characteristics of these castes and categories were also taken into account in religious beliefs), people's status was treated depending on their performance of various tasks. As a result, their activity had an impact on relationships in other processes. As stated in the third principle, consultations and councils, business dealings were conducted taking into account the interests of different classes. In such consultations and councils, from simple matters to issues of state management, the necessary conclusions were drawn. So, it turns out that the principles of Timurid were interconnected in the management of the kingdom, and they complemented each other, so that these connections and connections are a strong chain consisting of one ring. This chain arose from the events of the generality and is aimed at the management of a single kingdom. Therefore, the study of the state administration of Amir Temur, drawing modern necessary conclusions from "Tuzuklar" serves as an important factor in the development of Uzbekistan as a great country in the future. Amir Temur used the help of only 7 ministers in managing his country: 1. Minister of Country and Raiyat; 2. Minister of Security 3. Minister of Property, Income and Expenditure; 4. Sarkori is the minister in charge of affairs of the kingdom; 5. Qazi Kalon; 6. Jalal ul-Islam-king's supervisor with extraordinary rights; 7. The minister's office is a minister that contacts and conducts correspondence with various countries.

Tuzuklar is a logical result of Timurid's experience, and it is a work completed at the end of the nation's life. Amir Temur, recognizing the superior features of his state administration, wished that this administration would be continued as a tradition, "... So that the state and the kingdom will be saved from the damage and decline that will befall them from me", he made a hopeful will. In fact, the descendants of Amir Temur in different times, in different countries draw correct conclusions from this will, and therefore the Timurid dynasty ruled the countries for many centuries.

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